

INTERACTION OF HYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND THEIR
DERIVATIVES AND THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF
FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PART III. PREPARATION
OF 3:3'-DIACETYL-4:4'-DIHYDROXY-6:6'-DIPHENYL
THIOETHER AND ITS DERIVATIVES FROM
PEONOL

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3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethoxydiphenyl thioether, its phenylhydrazone, oxime, diacetyl and dibenzoyl derivatives and nitration and bromination products are described.

The reaction was carried out in presence of dry chloroform when the thioether was obtained. Its constitution was arrived at from the result of the action of nitric acid on it in cold acetic acid medium, when 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-nitroacetophenone (5-nitropeonol) was obtained. This showed that the two nuclei were linked through sulphur atom in the position which is *para* to OH and *meta* to COMe group. Its phenylhydrazone, oxime, diacetyl and dibenzoyl derivatives were prepared.

Bromination of the thioether with 2.5 molecules of bromine in acetic acid medium and continuous shaking for a long time gave 5-bromopeonol, which gave further support to the constitution. With excess of bromine in acetic acid medium and with a crystal of iodine it gave dibromopeonol, in which the other bromine atom might probably be in the side chain, as it was easily hydrolysed by heating with dilute alkali, and one bromine atom was lost.

The mechanism of the reaction may be explained in the same way as is done by Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1933, 2, Part II, 128; this *Journal*, 1934, 11, 551) as the same thioether is obtained by using sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride in presence of a few mg. of copper.

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethoxydiphenyl Thioether (I).—Peonol (12 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform (15 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (20 g.) was added to it, the flask being surrounded by crushed ice. Copper powder (8 g.) was gradually added and the whole mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Next day the mixture was heated for ten minutes on a water-bath at 60°. More dry chloroform was added and the solution boiled and filtered. Pasty mass remained behind after removal of the liquid, from which yellow solid was obtained after repeated treatment with acetone. It was finally crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles, m.p. 223-24°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: S, 8.6. C₁₈H₁₈O₆S requires S, 8.8 per cent).

It gave greenish coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and was found soluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and alcohol.

The same thioether was obtained when the ketone (2 g.) was treated with sulphur mono or dichloride (1 g.) in dry chloroform solution and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and heated on a boiling water-bath for about 20 minutes.

The following derivatives of the thioether were prepared.

The *phenylhydrazone* was prepared by heating it with phenylhydrazine in presence of acetic acid on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes. It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish white plates, m. p. 243-44°. (Found: N, 10.5. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 10.3 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared by heating it with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and caustic potash in presence of a little alcohol on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in pinkish white needles, m. p. 240-41°. (Found: N, 7.5. $C_{11}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.1 per cent).

The *Diacetate*.—Acetylation was carried out in presence of pyridine by boiling with acetic anhydride for 3 hours. It was crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m. p. 147-48°. (Found: S, 7.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.2 per cent).

The *Dibenzoate*.—Benzoylation was carried out in presence of pyridine by heating it for two hours with benzoyl chloride on a boiling water-bath. It crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid in brownish crystals, m. p. 172-73°. (Found: S, 5.7. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6S$ requires S, 5.6 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-nitroacetophenone.—The thioether (1, 1 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (10 c.c.), nitric acid (conc., 6 c.c.) was gradually added to it and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The solid obtained on diluting it with water was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 155°. (Found: N, 6.8. $C_9H_9O_5N$ requires N, 6.6 per cent). (cf. Roger Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 263).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-bromoacetophenone.—The thioether (1, 1 g.) was dissolved in boiling acetic acid (12 c.c.) and 15% solution of bromine (8 c.c.) was gradually added to the above solution at 90°. It was shaken for 8 hours on cooling and then left overnight. Acetic acid was allowed to evaporate at room temperature and after 3 days a solid separated. It was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 169-70°. (Found: Br, 32.4. $C_9H_9O_5Br$ requires Br, 32.6 per cent). (cf. Roger Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 261).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5:ω-dibromoacetophenone.—The thioether (1, 1 g.) was dissolved in boiling acetic acid (12 c.c.) and a crystal of iodine was added to it; 15% solution of bromine (18 c.c.) was added to it at 90°. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Next day it was poured into a dilute solution of sodium bisulphite when a pasty mass was obtained in pinkish granules, m. p. 72-73°. (Found: Br, 48.9. $C_9H_9O_5Br_2$ requires Br, 49.2 per cent).

The compound, when boiled with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, acidified with nitric acid and treated with silver nitrate solution, gave precipitate of silver bromide.